

PISCIVOROUS AVIFAUNA ON YELLOWSTONE LAKE,
YELLOWSTONE NATIONAL PARK

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ABSTRACT

In a natural area, piscivorous animals have priority over humans in the use of the fish resource. Thus it is necessary to understand the needs of the animals in order to keep human use to a non-conflicting level. This study was directed toward determining the consumption of cutthroat trout by the 13 major piscivorous species of avifauna on Yellowstone Lake, Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming. Population numbers and distribution were determined by censuses conducted during the summers of 1973 and 1974. Food habit information was obtained by field observations and a literature review. Population numbers were as follows: white pelicans-400 (1973), 195 (1974); ospreys-44, 42; common mergansers-616, 622; eared grebes-2582, 3071; Barrow's goldeneyes-1470, 1563; buffleheads-100, 93; bald eagles-17, 14; California gulls-2000, 1375; common loons-14, 2; double-crested cormorants-5, 17; great blue herons-14, 5; caspian terns-16, 23; belted kingfishers-8, 5. Ten of the species were densest in the arms of the lake, the exceptions being the ospreys with similar densities inside and outside the arms, the grebes on the open water, the kingfishers along the north shore, and the loons which showed no preference for any particular part of the lake. Individual pelicans were found to consume an average of 1.9 lb cutthroat trout/day, ospreys 0.88 lb/day, mergansers 0.9 lb/day, grebes 0.31 lb/day, goldeneyes 0.005 lb/day, buffleheads 0.01 lb/day, eagles 0.09 lb/day, gulls 0.34 lb/day, loons 1.19 lb/day, cormorants 0.003 lb/day, terns 0.7 lb/day, and kingfishers 0.3 lb/day. It was determined that a young pelican utilized 102 lb of cutthroat trout during the rearing period, and a young osprey 61 lb. Total consumption for a 100-day period was 257,967 lb of cutthroat trout in 1973, and 184,635 in 1974. Since mortality in young cutthroat was considered to have no effect on the ultimate size of the adult fish population, the biomass taken by grebes, buffleheads, gulls, loons, terns, and kingfishers was subtracted from the total, leaving a net consumption of 224,993 lb in 1973, and 144,223 lb in 1974.

INTRODUCTION

Yellowstone National Park has been designated as a natural area. In such areas, management is directed toward maintaining a pristine condition with human influence kept to a minimum (Houston 1971).

The fishery in this park, in particular that in Yellowstone Lake, is a complex system in which man has a part. As a fisherman he acts as a predator on cutthroat trout populations, as do bears, otters, pelicans, ospreys, large trout, and others. These animals depend on the fish as a food source and in a natural area have priority over man in the use of this resource. Thus it is important to understand their needs from the fishery so that man's use of the resource can be held to a non-conflicting level.

This report pursues the question of predation on fish by the avifauna on the lake. Based on a preliminary literature review and a census of the bird populations conducted during the summer of 1973, it was decided to limit the discussion to the following species of birds, listed in order of their projected importance: white pelican (*Pelecanus occidentalis*), osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*), common merganser (*Mergus merganser*), eared grebe (*Podiceps caspicus*), Barrow's goldeneye (*Bucephala islandica*), bufflehead (*Bucephala albeola*), bald eagle (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*), California gull (*Larus californicus*), common loon (*Gavia immer*), double-crested cormorant (*Phalacrocorax*

auritus), great blue heron (*Ardea herodias*), caspian tern (*Hydroprogne caspia*), and belted kingfisher (*Megaceryle alcyon*). Using data on numbers of birds, their seasonal use of the lake, and their daily rates of fish consumption, an estimate of the biomass of cutthroat trout that the piscivorous birds on Yellowstone Lake consume will be made.

METHODS

Census

The shoreline of the lake and the three major islands was divided into 24 five-mile sections which were numbered for identification purposes (Fig. 1). The thirteen species of birds were censused section by section. All individuals that could be seen from a boat moving along the shoreline approximately 30-50 ft offshore were identified with the aid of a 7x35 binocular and counted. Most areas were censused from a powerboat; those sections in the hand-propelled craft zones of the lake were done from a canoe. Weather permitting, a section was visited each morning or evening within 3-4 hr of sunrise or sunset, respectively.

The census was conducted four times: 24 July- 19 August 1973, 28 September- 7 October 1973, 12-30 June 1974, and 30 July- 27 August 1974. Not all of the 24 areas were censused during the two 1973 census periods. For the earlier count, 18 areas were chosen randomly, censused, and the numbers expanded to obtain total shoreline population estimates. For the later count, there was only time to census nine randomly chosen areas, so the numbers obtained during this period will only be used to indicate late fall trends in population size. All 24 areas were counted for the first 1974 census and all but one for the last, with the sequence being dictated by convenience.

Figure 1. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the 24 census sections.

During each census period, in addition to the shoreline counts, open water counts were made. These were transects of the lake, chosen randomly, which were traversed in a powerboat. All birds that could be seen ahead or 150 yards to the starboard and 70 yards to the port side of the boat were counted. These counts were also made within 3-4 hr of sunrise or sunset. During the first count in 1973, 18.7 square miles (14 percent of the open water) were covered; during the second count in 1973--10 square miles (7%); during the first count in 1974--40 square miles (31%); and during the second count in 1974--40 square miles (30%). Numbers from each of these census periods, except the second in 1973, were expanded to obtain the total number of birds on the open water.

Also during each census period, except the second in 1973, the Molly Islands were visited one morning and the birds present at the time were counted.

Numbers from all three areas (shoreline, open water, and the Molly Islands) were added together to give total population estimates for each species of bird.

Observations in the Field

Observations of feeding behavior were made with a 7x35 binocular and a variable power (15-60x) spotting scope from the shore in areas where the birds were actively feeding. Buffleheads, goldeneyes, and mergansers in the South Arm and Flat Mountain Arm were watched at

various times of the day. In addition, mergansers were watched for two complete days (sunrise to sunset) as they fed on the Yellowstone River just below Fishing Bridge and for two complete days in Eagle Bay. Observations were also made at two different osprey nests, one with one young and one with two young, on five different days. On the days when a nest was not observed for the entire daylight period, an estimate was made of the number of additional fish which would have been brought to the nest based on the number recorded during the observation period.

Stomach Analysis

A permit to shoot 12 birds for stomach analyses was obtained. The birds were to be 8 mergansers, 2 buffleheads, and 2 goldeneyes. Four mergansers were to be taken before the trout eggs hatched and fry began migration to the lake; the other eight birds were to be taken during the period of fry migration. Three mergansers were collected. For reasons to be discussed below, the remaining nine birds were not collected.

Collecting Fish Remains from the Molly Islands

On 5 September 1974, fish bones from Sandy and Rocky Islands were collected. These were sorted according to type, i.e., vertebrae, opercular bones, maxillaries, etc.

During the U. S. Fish and Wildlife fall gill-netting operation of 1974, cutthroat trout and longnose suckers of various sizes were

collected. The bones from the Molly Islands were compared with the bones of these known specimens.

Literature Review

The literature was searched for studies done on the food habits of the thirteen species, their daily rates of food consumption, and the size and species composition of the fish taken. In addition, information on density-dependent mortality in young cutthroat trout was reviewed.

RESULTS

Census

Population Numbers

Total population numbers were computed for the thirteen species for the July-August 1973, June 1974, and July-August 1974 censuses (Table I).

TABLE I. CENSUS DATA FOR THE THIRTEEN SPECIES FOR THE JULY-AUGUST 1973, JUNE 1974, AND JULY-AUGUST 1974 CENSUSES.

	July- August 1973	Independent Researchers June 1973	June 1974	Independent Researchers June 1974	July- August 1974
Pelican	347	400 (Diem)	364	208 (Diem)	25
Osprey	23	44 (Swenson)	31	42 (Swenson)	39
Merganser	616		465		779
Grebe	2582		40		3031
Goldeneye	1470		1220		1906
Bufflehead	100		123		63
Eagle	13	17 (Swenson)	7	14 (Swenson)	7
Gull	1587	2000 (Diem)	1400		1350
Loon	14		1		3
Cormorant	5	5 (Diem)	16		18
Heron	14		5		4
Tern	6	26 (Diem)	43	30-35 (Diem)	2
Kingfisher	8		7		3

During the late summer, grebes were the most numerous waterbirds. At other times, in descending numerical order, the gulls, goldeneyes, mergansers, pelicans, and buffleheads were the most numerous. The other species were less abundant, each numbering fewer than 50 for each of the counts.

For comparison, the population numbers determined by independent researchers are included (Table I). Figures for the osprey were based on a count of active nests and for the bald eagle were based on a count of active nests and observations of different immature nonbreeders. Figures for the pelicans and terns were based on counts of active nests on the Molly Islands, and for the cormorants and gulls on estimates of adults on the islands at a given time.

For the ospreys and eagles, figures from this study were consistently lower than those of Swenson. The 1973 figures for pelicans, terns, and gulls were lower than those obtained by Diem, particularly for the terns; however, for June 1974, figures from this study were higher. Reasons for these differences will be presented in the discussion.

The census for October 1973 was treated separately. A comparison was made of the population numbers of birds in shoreline areas 2, 6, 10, 11, 15, 16, 18, 21, and 22 (the nine areas censused) and the open water censused (unexpanded but adjusted numbers) for all four census periods (Table II). Although the data were limited, they showed the disappearance of pelicans, terns, and cormorants from the counts in October, a decrease in numbers of ospreys, mergansers, grebes, buffleheads, gulls, herons, and kingfishers, and an increase in numbers of goldeneyes, eagles and loons. Because of these observed changes, when computing the consumption of fish by these birds, only the time period

TABLE II. CENSUS DATA FROM NINE CENSUSED AREAS AND OPEN WATER FOR ALL FOUR CENSUS PERIODS.

Species	July-August 1973	October 1973	June 1974	July-August 1974
Pelican	23	0	40	18
Osprey	10	2	10	17
Merganser	170	66	122	73
Grebe	206	26	4	241
Goldeneye	274	876	312	344
Bufflehead	17	14	31	2
Eagle	7	8	1	0
Gull	134	61	207	168
Loon	1	7	0	0
Cormorant	0	0	0	0
Heron	4	1	3	1
Tern	2	0	2	1
Kingfisher	5	1	4	1

between 1 June (when the ice breaks off the lake) and 8 September (prior to the beginning of migration) will be considered. This is a one-hundred day period. For the 1973 computations Swenson's population numbers for eagles and ospreys will be used, as will Diem's population numbers for the pelicans, cormorants, gulls, and terns, and the author's population estimates for the loons, grebes, herons, buffleheads, goldeneyes, mergansers, and kingfishers. In the 1974 computations, for eagles and ospreys Swenson's population numbers will be used, for grebes the author's estimates from the June counts will be used for June and July, and from the July-August count for August to 8 September. For the other ten species an average of the numbers from the two counts will be used (Table III).

TABLE III. COMPUTATION OF BIRD-DAYS.

Species	1973 Population Numbers (A)	1974 Population Numbers (B)	No. of Days (C)	No. of Bird-Days 1973 (A x C)	No. of Bird-Days 1974 (B x C)
Pelican	400	195	100	40,000	19,500
Osprey	44	42	100	4,400	4,200
Merganser	616	622	100	61,600	62,200
Grebe	2582	3031	39	90,698	120,649
	0	40	61		
Goldeneye	1470	1563	100	147,000	156,300
Bufflehead	100	93	100	10,000	9,300
Eagle	17	14	100	1,700	1,400
Gull	2000	1375	100	200,000	137,500
Loon	14	2	100	1,400	200
Cormorant	5	17	100	500	1,700
Heron	14	5	100	1,400	500
Tern	16	23	100	1,600	2,300
Kingfisher	8	5	100	800	500

Distribution

Specific distributional maps are presented for the 13 species for three of the census periods (Figs. 2-14, in the appendix). The distributions of these species in three divisions of the lake are also given (Tables IV-VI).

In late summer 1973, with the exception of the pelicans, grebes, and kingfishers, over half of each of the species was observed in the arms. The majority of the pelicans were seen on the open water, all the grebes were on the open water, and the kingfishers were outside the arms, four of the six being along the north shore. Although ten species were observed most frequently in the arms, when considering the total

TABLE IV. DISTRIBUTION OF PISCIVOROUS BIRDS IN THREE DIVISIONS OF THE LAKE: JULY-AUGUST 1973.

	Inside the Arms				Total No. (% of total)	Outside the Arms				Total	Open Water		
	Southeast Arm (4,5)	South Arm (8,9)	Flat Mtn. Arm (12,14)	Thumb (15,16)		West Shore (19,16)	North Shore (21,22)	East Shore (23,1,2)	Other (11,14)				
Pelican	129	6	11	0	146(43.6)	1	0	0	0	0	2	3(0.9)	186(56.5)
Osprey	0	3	4	4	11(68.8)	4	0	0	0	0	1	5(31.2)	0(0.0)
Merganser	162	0	97	9	268(55.1)	86	4	0	0	18	60	168(34.6)	50(10.3)
Grebe	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	2582(100.0)
Goldeneye	422	38	248	88	796(74.7)	120	16	0	8	1	39	184(17.3)	86(8.0)
Bufflehead	6	0	47	2	55(77.5)	16	0	0	0	0	0	16(22.5)	0(0.0)
Eagle	0	0	2	1	3(33.3)	1	0	3	1	1	1	6(66.7)	0(0.0)
Gull	1018	13	15	9	1055(70.2)	72	9	26	35	6	6	148(9.8)	300(20.0)
Loon	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	14(100.0)
Cormorant	5	0	0	0	5(100.0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Heron	1	1	4	1	7(70.0)	2	0	0	0	0	1	3(30.0)	0(0.0)
Tern	1	0	1	0	2(50.0)	0	0	2	0	0	0	2(50.0)	0(0.0)
Kingfisher	0	0	1	0	1(16.7)	1	0	0	4	0	0	5(83.3)	0(0.0)
Total	1744	61	430	114	2349(38.5)	303	29	43	55	110	540(8.8)	3218(52.7)	

TABLE V. DISTRIBUTION OF PISCIVOROUS BIRDS IN THREE DIVISIONS OF THE LAKE: JUNE 1974.

	Inside the Arms				Total No. (% of total)	Outside the Arms				Total	Open Water				
	Southeast Arm (4,5)(3,6)	South Arm (8,9)(7,10)	Fiat Mtn. Arm (12,13)	Thumb (15,16, 17,18)		West Shore (19,20)	North Shore (21,22)	East Shore (23,1,2)	Other (11,14)(24)						
Pelican	216	0	50	26	16	308(84.6)	0	0	10	0	0	0	10(2.7)	46(12.7)	
Osprey	0	1	5	5	0	11(3.5)	2	2	1	1	1	3	8	17(54.8)	3(9.7)
Merganser	35	5	118	70	97	325(69.9)	58	0	7	0	0	59	0	124(26.7)	16(3.4)
Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1(2.5)	39(97.5)
Goldeneye	335	80	168	110	115	808(66.2)	78	27	53	20	82	80	0	340(27.9)	72(5.9)
Bufflehead	16	3	46	14	11	90(73.2)	10	3	9	2	6	0	0	30(24.4)	3(2.4)
Eagle	0	0	6	0	0	6(85.7)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1(14.3)	0(0.0)
Gull	841	29	54	35	7	966(69.0)	56	9	47	62	13	2	2	189(13.5)	245(17.5)
Loon	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1(100.0)	0(0.0)
Cormorant	16	0	0	0	0	16(100.0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Heron	1	0	0	0	0	1(20.0)	0	1	3	0	0	0	0	4(80.0)	0(0.0)
Tern	28	0	4	0	0	32(74.4)	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1(2.3)	10(23.3)
Kingfisher	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0	3	4	0	0	0	0	7(100.0)	0(0.0)
Total	1488	118	451	260	246	2563(68.9)	206	46	134	86	163	90	725(19.5)	434(11.6)	

TABLE V. DISTRIBUTION OF PISCIVOROUS BIRDS IN THREE DIVISIONS OF THE LAKE: JUNE 1974.

	Inside the Arms				Outside the Arms				Total	Open Water				
	Southeast Arm (4,5)(3,6)	South Arm (8,9)(7,10)	Flat Mtn. Arm (12,13)	Total No. (% of total)	Thumb (15,16, 17,18)	West Shore (19,20)	North Shore (21,22)	East Shore (23,1,2)			Other (11,14)(24)			
Pelican	216	0	50	26	16	308(84.6)	0	0	0	0	10(2.7)	46(12.7)		
Osprey	0	1	5	5	0	11(3.5)	2	2	1	3	8	17(54.8)	3(9.7)	
Merganser	35	5	118	70	97	325(69.9)	58	0	7	0	59	124(26.7)	16(3.4)	
Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	1	0	0	0	0	1(2.5)	39(97.5)	
Goldeneye	335	80	168	110	115	808(66.2)	78	27	53	20	82	340(27.9)	72(5.9)	
Bufflehead	16	3	46	14	11	90(73.2)	10	3	9	2	6	30(24.4)	3(2.4)	
Eagle	0	0	6	0	0	6(85.7)	1	0	0	0	0	1(14.3)	0(0.0)	
Gull	841	29	54	35	7	966(69.0)	56	9	47	62	13	2	189(13.5)	245(17.5)
Loon	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0	1	0	0	0	0	1(100.0)	0(0.0)
Cormorant	16	0	0	0	0	16(100.0)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Heron	1	0	0	0	0	1(20.0)	0	1	3	0	0	0	4(80.0)	0(0.0)
Tern	28	0	4	0	0	32(74.4)	0	0	0	1	0	0	1(2.3)	10(23.3)
Kingfisher	0	0	0	0	0	0.(0.0)	0	3	4	0	0	0	7(100.0)	0(0.0)
Total	1488	118	451	260	246	2563(68.9)	206	46	134	86	163	90	725(19.5)	434(11.6)

number of birds, over half were found on the open water. This was due to the large number of grebes and their seeming proclivity for the open water.

In June of 1974, the species whose numbers were found largely outside the arms were the ospreys, grebes, loons, herons, and kingfishers. Again the grebes were on the open water and the kingfishers in the northern part of the lake. Loons and herons were also found largely in the northern part of the lake. The largest number of ospreys was located outside the arms. The total number of all species indicated that at this time the majority of the birds were in the arms.

In late summer 1974, three species, grebes, kingfishers, and ospreys, were found largely outside the arms. The grebes and kingfishers followed the same pattern as in late summer 1973. Considering the totals, the numbers inside the arms and on the open water were similar.

If one considers the densities of the birds in the three divisions of the lake (Table VII), a more consistent pattern develops. With a few exceptions, density of each species is greatest inside the arms. The exceptions are the kingfishers along the north shore of the lake, the grebes in the late summer on the open water, the osprey which has approximately equal densities inside and outside the arms, and the loons which do not seem to show any consistency about the part of the lake used. Then the totals are considered, the birds are definitely

TABLE VII. POPULATION DENSITIES IN THE THREE DIVISIONS OF THE LAKE, EXPRESSED IN BIRDS/SQ. MI.

Species	July-August 1973			June 1974			July-August 1974		
	Inside Arms	Outside Arms	Open Water	Inside Arms	Outside Arms	Open Water	Inside Arms	Outside Arms	Open Water
Pelican	214.7	2.4	1.4	256.7	6.2	0.34	20.8	0.0	0.0
Osprey	16.2	4.0	0.0	9.2	10.6	0.02	9.2	13.1	0.05
Merganser	394.1	134.4	0.4	270.8	77.5	0.12	543.3	77.5	0.02
Grebe	0.0	0.0	19.3	0.0	0.6	0.29	0.8	8.1	22.5
Goldeneye	1170.6	147.2	0.6	673.3	212.5	0.54	1166.7	295.6	0.25
Bufflehead	80.9	12.8	0.0	75.0	18.8	0.02	42.5	1.2	0.0
Eagle	4.4	4.8	0.0	5.0	0.6	0.0	5.0	0.6	0.0
Gull	1331.3	118.4	2.2	805.0	118.1	1.83	800.8	159.4	1.0
Loon	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.6	0.0	2.5	0.0	0.0
Cormorant	7.4	0.0	0.0	13.3	0.0	0.0	15.0	0.0	0.0
Heron	10.3	2.4	0.0	0.8	2.5	0.0	2.5	0.6	0.0
Tern	2.9	1.6	0.0	26.7	0.6	0.07	0.8	0.6	0.0
Kingfisher	1.5	4.0	0.0	0.0	4.4	0.0	0.0	1.9	0.0
Total	1957.5	337.5	24.0	2135.8	453.1	3.2	2618.3	558.8	23.9

densest inside the arms at all times of the summer.

Feeding Observations

Pelicans

On 20 June 1974 six pelicans were observed while feeding intermittently from 9:30 a.m. to 2:30 p.m. They were not always within sight, so an estimate of the number or biomass of fish taken in this time period was not made. But, three fish were caught when the pelicans were visible; these were trout approximately 4-6 in. long.

Both on the Yellowstone River and in Eagle Bay there were frequently one or more pelicans associated with feeding mergansers. Almost invariably when a merganser surfaced with a fish, one to four pelicans would attempt to take the fish. Of 45 such attempts, only 3 were successful. The pelicans did not exhibit any other feeding behavior when associated with the mergansers.

Ospreys

At the osprey nest with one young, 6 fish/day were brought to the nest when the chick was approximately 18 days old, 6 fish/day were brought when it was approximately 29 days old, and 4 fish/day were brought when it was approximately 42 days old. At the osprey nest with two young, 6-8 fish/day were brought to the nest when the chicks were approximately 25 days old. Swenson (pers. comm.) indicated that 5 fish/day were brought to a nest with two chicks 52 days old.

All the fish observed were trout 10-12 in. long. Swenson (pers. comm.) has found that ospreys take fish averaging approximately 11 in. long; based on bones collected from nests in the southern part of the lake he found that their diet consisted of 88.5 percent cutthroat trout, 6.6 percent longnose sucker, 3.3 percent unidentified fish, and 1.6 percent frogs. When only the identified fish bones were considered, this became 93.1 percent cutthroat, and 6.9 percent longnose sucker.

Based on the number and species composition of fish that were observed brought to the osprey nests, the amount of fish required to raise a young to the fledgling stage (50-51 days, Garber 1972) can be computed. Through the early brooding period, the male provides both the young and the female with fish. By the time the young are six weeks old, they can feed themselves and both parents provide them with fish (MacCarter 1972). It has been observed that one or both parents eat away from the nest (MacCarter 1972, Ueoka 1974). This indicates that from 0-41 days, fish which are brought to the nest are shared by the young and the female, while after this time the fish are eaten only by the young. Results from this study showed that 6 fish/day were brought to a nest with one young while the female was feeding it, and 4 fish/day when it reached six weeks and could feed itself. Since there is no way of knowing how many of the six fish were eaten by the female and how many eaten by the young, the number was arbitrarily divided in half. Thus from 0-41 days this young ate 3 fish/day, which

is about 1.5 lb/day (an 11 in. cutthroat trout weighs about 0.5 lb, Dean and Varley 1973), and from 42-50 days ate 4 fish/day, which is about 2 lb/day. Thus an estimated 77.5 lb of cutthroat trout were needed to raise this young to the fledgling stage. Repeating this for the nest with two young gives an estimate of 61.3 lb of fish needed to raise each one. An average derived from nests with one and two young, is 69.4 lb.

Mergansers

On the Yellowstone River, although at least one of a group of 100-150 mergansers was feeding all the time, there appeared to be three peaks in the feeding activity: one in the morning, one between noon and 3:00 p.m., and a third in the evening. The group of 12-15 mergansers in Eagle Bay fed only twice a day, once in the morning, and once in the evening. And a group of six in the South Arm were actively feeding in the afternoon between 3:00 and 4:00. Thus it seems that mergansers have 2-3 periods of intensive feeding per day.

During periods of observation 53 fish were brought to the surface and eaten by mergansers. All of these were trout, ranging from 6-11 in. Hoskins (pers. comm.) observed a group of mergansers on shore that were feeding on fish which ranged in size from 8-11 in. An overall average size for the fish taken is approximately 8.5 in. The consumption of a fish this size resulted in a cessation in feeding activity by the individual, suggesting a sufficient volume for the feeding period had

been eaten. Thus an individual merganser may eat two to three 8.5 in. fish per day, which is approximately 0.44-0.66 lb fish/day (an 8.5 in. cutthroat weighs approximately 0.22 lb, Dean and Varley 1973).

Both in the South Arm and on the Yellowstone River, mergansers fed in shallow water and appeared to be feeding on the bottom and under rocks and logs. Also at the mouth of Grouse Creek in the South Arm, 2-3 mergansers were observed to be feeding among the sedges. These birds may have been eating food other than fish. This has been reported by Bent (1923) and Kortright (1943).

Goldeneyes and Buffleheads

Observations of feeding goldeneyes and buffleheads revealed little about their diets. Although several hundred dives were watched, no bird was observed to surface with a fish, nor was it possible to detect what, if anything, was brought up from a dive. The depth of the water in which they were observed to dive varied from less than a foot to greater than 30 feet.

Eagles

Field observations of bald eagle food habits were not made in this study; however, Swenson (pers. comm.) analyzed food items collected from eagle nests and found that their diet consisted of birds (57.9%), fish (24.6%), and mammals (17.5%). Dividing the fish category into species indicated that the diet was 12.3 percent cutthroat trout, 7.0 percent longnose sucker, 1.8 percent Utah sucker, and 3.5 percent

unidentified fish.

Stomach Analysis

Of the three mergansers shot, one had nine fish vertebrae and some obsidian sand in its stomach and gizzard, and the other two had only obsidian sand.

Bones Collected from the Molly Islands

Of the 1202 bones collected from the Molly Islands, 68.3 percent were from cutthroat trout, 14.3 percent were from Utah chubs, 9.8 percent were from longnose suckers, 7.2 percent were from unidentified fish, and 0.4 percent were from mammals and birds. Of the trout bones 450 were whole enough to compare their sizes with ones from 32 fish of known sizes, range 3-15 in. All 450 came from trout larger than 9.0 in., 2.7 percent from trout 9.0-11.0 in. long, 15.3 percent from trout 11.1-13 in. long, 67.1 percent from trout 13.1-15 in. long, and 14.9 percent from trout longer than 15 in. Although the usable sucker bones were less numerous, it was possible to compare 28 opercular bones collected from the islands with 100 comparable bones from fish of known length ranging from 4 to 20 in.; 32.2 percent were from suckers 8-12 in. long, 48.3 percent from suckers 12.1-16 in. long, 12.9 percent from suckers 16.1-20 in. long, and 6.4 percent from suckers longer than 20 in. Having no bones with which to compare those of the Utah chub, it was not possible to determine the distribution of sizes, however, Baxter (pers. comm.) estimated they were from fish 8-12 in. long.

Since the bones collected were from fish longer than 8 in., it was assumed that they represented fish taken by pelicans. The maximum size of fish taken by terns and cormorants is 5-6 in. (Diem, pers. comm., Bartholomew 1942); while gulls do prey on large fish, this is mainly in the spawning streams and it is unlikely they would carry fish of this size to the islands. Thus, the species composition of the fish bones is indicative of the species composition of the pelican's diet in Yellowstone National Park.

Literature Review

The diet of the pelican is entirely fish (Bent 1922, Ward 1922, Hall 1925). This species has been reported to eat up to 8 lb of fish per day (Maynard 1896, Ward 1922), but this estimate is probably high. More reasonable estimates of daily food consumption ranged from 2 to 4 lb/day and averaged 2.8 lb/day (Hall 1925, Schaller 1962, Bell pers. comm.). Hall (1925) estimated that it would take 150 lb to raise a young white pelican to 64 days. Ward (1922) reported that in Yellowstone National Park trout, in the absence of other fish, made up 98-100 percent of the diet, particularly during the trout spawning season when the fish are particularly vulnerable. Longnose suckers, however, have been introduced to the lake population of fishes since this time (Benson 1961) and probably make up part of the diet of the pelican. Pelicans ate fish from 1 to 27 in., and usually took those in the 3-15 in. range (Hall 1925).

The diet of the osprey consists entirely of fish (Bent 1937). An adult consumes about 1.7-1.8 fish/day (Brown and Amadon 1968), which in terms of 11 in. trout is about 1 lb fish/day. Although three studies have been made on the number of fish provided to various size broods, there is no accurate way to convert the data provided to biomass.

Mergansers are primarily fish eating birds, although they do feed to a lesser extent on molluscs, crustaceans, water insects and their larvae, and aquatic plants (Bent 1923, Kortright 1943). Estimates of daily fish consumption ranged from 0.38 lb/day to 1.4 lb/day with an average of 0.96 lb/day (Audubon 1843, White 1937, 1939, 1957, Sayler and Langler 1940, Lindroth 1955, Elson 1962, Latta and Sharkey 1966, Meigs and Rieck 1967). They will take whatever kind of fish is most readily available, and on trout waters, trout were found to make up 87.9 percent of their diet (Sayler and Langler 1940). The size of fish taken averaged 5-6 in. for salmonids (White 1937, Alcorn 1953), and ranged from 1 to 14 1/2 in. (Sayler and Langler 1940, Alcorn 1953, White 1957, Huntington and Roberts 1959, Elson 1962, Meigs and Rieck 1967). On inland lakes and rivers mergansers showed a preference for larger fishes (Sayler and Langler 1940, Elson 1962).

Food of the eared grebe consists mainly of water insects, their larvae, land insects drifting on the water, caterpillars, and tadpoles, although small fish are occasionally taken (Bent 1919, Roberts 1932, Munro 1941, Martin *et al.* 1951, Dawn 1959, Palmer 1962). Pied-billed

grebes, approximately the same size as eared grebes, took fish no bigger than 5 in. (Ladhams 1968).

Animal food dominates the diet of the goldeneye, but few fish are taken (Munro 1918, Bent 1925, Martin *et al.* 1957). It was estimated that one percent of the volume of their diet is fish (Cottam 1939, Kortright 1943). The common goldeneye and other carnivorous waterbirds similar in size and weight were found to consume about 0.47 lb food/day (Nilsson 1969), a figure to be used for the Barrow's goldeneye. White (1939) reported that these birds took salmon parr up to 4 in. long.

Buffleheads feed chiefly on animal food, fish making up about four percent of the diet (Bent 1925, Cottam 1939, Munro 1942, Kortright 1943, Martin *et al.* 1951, Erskine 1972).

Bald eagles eat mammals and birds as well as fish (Bent 1937, Murie 1940, Imer and Kalmabach 1955, Retfalvi 1970, Rossman *et al.* 1971). Consumption rates for captive eagles ranged from 0.59 to 1.0 lb/day, averaging 0.71 lb/day (Chura and Stewart 1967, Stewart 1970, Rossman *et al.* 1971).

California gulls are omnivorous and probably feed to some extent on fish (Bent 1921, Cottam 1945, Greenhalgh 1952, Rothweiler 1960, Vermeer 1970). In Yellowstone Park they have been observed to eat large numbers of small fingerlings in shallow water, and to prey on spawning fish ascending the streams (Woodbury n.d.).

Fish are the main food item in the diet of the loon, although molluscs, amphipods, aquatic insects, and vegetation are also eaten (McAtee 1919, Munro 1945, Olson and Marshall 1952, Martin *et al.* 1957, Palmer 1962). Estimates on the percentage of fish in the diet range from 80 percent (McAtee 1919) to 100 percent (Olson and Marshall 1952). Fish taken ranged from 3 to 6 in. (Bent 1919, Sim 1923, Forbush 1929).

The diet of the double-crested cormorant consists mainly of fish (Taverner 1915, Bent 1922, Lewis 1929, Mendall 1936, Bartholomew 1942, Palmer 1962). Estimates of the consumption rates ranged from 0.73 to 3 lb/day, with an average of 1.3 lb/day (Taverner 1915, Wetmore 1927, Bartholomew 1942, Junor 1972). Although the diet consists of fish, a summary of over 141 records of the types of food eaten in fresh water habitats showed that only 0.2 percent of the total volume was trout (Mendall 1936). In addition, Lewis (1929) found that trout and salmon appeared "distasteful if not positively harmful" to captive birds. Cormorants were not first observed in Yellowstone National Park until 1928 (Skinner 1929), which was 4-5 years after the introduction of long-nose suckers into Yellowstone Lake (Benson 1961). Cormorants seldom caught fish greater than 5-6 in. long (Bartholomew 1942).

The principal food of the great blue heron is fish, but frogs, crayfish, small snakes, salamanders, insects, and meadow mice are also eaten (Barrows 1912, Bent 1926, Cottam and Uhler 1945, Palmer 1962). Based on a collection of the contents of 189 stomachs from herons

throughout the United States it was found that fish made up 71.6 percent of the heron diet (Cottam and Uhler 1945). Of the fish, 32 percent were game fish, while 68 percent were non-game or unidentified fish. Adults of four species of hand-raised African herons consumed 16 percent of their body weight (Junor 1972). Applying this to the great blue heron yields an estimate of 1.93 lb food consumed/day. Sizes of fish taken ranged from 2 to 16 in. (White 1939, Lopinot 1950).

Caspian terns eat mostly small fish, but probably also feed on shrimps and other forms of surface swimming aquatic life (Bent 1921, Diem pers. comm.). They take fish 4-8 in. long (DeGroot 1931), although Diem (pers. comm.) estimated that they took fish only to 4-5 in. on Yellowstone Lake.

Bent (1940) stated that in Yellowstone National Park the kingfisher probably lives entirely on fish. Two captive young kingfishers ate 4-7 oz of fish/day, which was 1-1 3/4 times their weight. Assuming an adult would eat as much as its own weight (6 oz, Sayler and Langler 1949) in food/day, this would amount to 0.37 lb/day. They will eat whatever species is most available, taking those found in approximately two feet of water or within two feet of the top of deeper water (White 1953). Cornwell (1962) found that in trout waters, 80.1 percent of the fish taken were trout. The mean length of fish taken by adults was approximately 3 in., and although the range was 1-7 in., most fish were under 5 in. (Peterson 1935, White 1937, Cornwell 1963).

From reports in the literature estimates of daily rates of consumption for the cormorant, pelican, goldeneye, merganser, bald eagle, osprey, heron, and kingfisher were determined. By plotting the weights of these species versus the amount of food consumed/day (expressed as a percentage of their body weights) on a graph, it was possible to estimate the daily consumption rates of the other five species: loon--1.91 lb/day; grebe--0.31 lb/day; bufflehead--0.34 lb/day; tern--0.7 lb/day; gull--0.67 lb/day.

The computation of the biomass of cutthroat trout taken by piscivorous avifauna was based on the number of bird-days (Table III), the amount of food eaten per bird per day, the percentage of this total amount that is fish, and the percentage of fish taken that is cutthroat trout (Table VIII). The amount of food eaten per bird per day and the percentage of this which consists of fish was largely taken from the data presented in the literature. Percentages were available for all species except the grebes and the gulls. Since the grebes were found on the open water, and the only prey item of any size there is fish (Benson 1961), their diet was assumed to consist entirely of fish. For the gulls 50 percent was arbitrarily chosen as the percentage of fish in the diet. The percentage of fish that is cutthroat trout was derived in part from field data from this study, Swenson's field data, and data reported in the literature. Where data were not available, it was assumed that the portion of the diet that is fish consisted entirely

TABLE VIII. COMPUTED BIOMASS OF CUTTHROAT TROUT CONSUMED BY PISCIVOROUS AVIFAUNA DURING A 100-DAY PERIOD IN 1973 AND 1974.

Species	No. of bird-days		Lb. food eaten/day	% Food that is fish	% Fish that is trout	Total consumption	
	1973	1974				1973	1974
Pelican	40,000	19,500	2.8	100	68	76,100	37,100
Osprey	4,400	4,200	1.0	100	88	3,872	3,696
Merganser	61,600	62,200	0.96	100	94	54,429	56,129
Grebe	90,698	120,649	0.31	100	100	28,116	37,401
Goldeneye	147,000	156,300	0.47	1	100	691	735
Bufflehead	10,000	9,300	0.34	4	100	136	126
Eagle	1,700	1,400	0.71	25	50	145	119
Gull	200,000	137,500	0.67	50	100	67,000	46,062
Loon	1,400	200	1.91	100	100	2,674	382
Cormorant	500	1,700	1.3	100	0.2	1	4
Heron	1,400	500	1.93	72	100	1,946	695
Tern	1,600	2,300	0.7	100	100	1,120	1,610
Kingfisher	800	500	0.37	100	80	237	148
					Subtotal	236,467	184,207
Young pelican	1973	203	150	0.68		20,706	
	1974	0					
Young osprey	1973	13	69.4	0.88		794	
	1974	7					428
					Total	257,967	184,635

of cutthroat trout. In addition, the biomass required to raise young pelicans and young ospreys to the fledgling stage were included. Thus a computed 257,967 lb of cutthroat trout were consumed in a 100-day period in 1973, and 184,635 in 1974 by the major piscivorous avifauna.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The validity of the census method is based on several assumptions:

1) that the birds were tied to the water by their feeding habits, nesting habits, and general behavior; 2) that the periods of highest activity, and thus the time when they would be most visible for counting, were the mornings and the evenings when they were actively feeding; and 3) that within a census period distribution of the birds was fairly constant.

No attempt was made in the field to check the validity of these assumptions. Literature review indicates that the first and second are basically sound (Taverner 1915, Bent 1919, 1921, 1922, 1923, 1925, 1937, 1940, Hall 1925, Sayler and Langler 1940, Kortright 1943, Lopinot 1950, Delacour 1954, Rothweiler 1960, Schaller 1964). Several species, such as the bufflehead, kingfisher, loon, and osprey, feed throughout the day (Sim 1920, White 1936, MacCarter 1972, Erskine 1972), but would also be active in the morning and evening hours. Evaluation of the last assumption is impossible without further field data; however, information which has been gathered to date suggests its validity. Kingfishers were generally found along the north shore, ospreys were abundant on Frank Island and in the arms, grebes showed a proclivity for the open water in the late summer, pelicans, gulls, terns, and cormorants seemed to center their activities around the Molly Islands, and total numbers of birds were always low along the east and north shores

and high inside the arms.

The population numbers are by nature of the census minimal. Ease in sighting waterbirds was related to their size, coloring, and behavior patterns. Eagles and ospreys were conspicuous in shoreline trees because of their size and white markings, but difficult to see when soaring at a distance, crouched in a nest or perched in a tree away from the shore. Herons and kingfishers, darker in coloration, were readily seen when in motion, but were well camouflaged when motionless. Loons, female goldeneyes, and buffleheads, also dark in color, were easier to see because they spent most of their time on the water. Terns, gulls, and pelicans were conspicuous because of their white color, cormorants easy to count because of their affinity for a given location. Mergansers on shore were hard to see at first because of their coloring, but were seldom missed because they moved onto the water at the approach of a boat. Large rafts of birds were hard to count accurately, although the gregariousness of grebes made them easy to see on the open water.

Population estimates were different from those of other researchers. This discrepancy was probably due to differences in the census methods and times at which the birds were counted.

Diem's figures for pelicans and terns were based on June counts of active nests on the Molly Islands, and for the cormorants and gulls, on June estimates of adults on the islands at a given time. For the pelicans in 1973, the author's population estimate was lower than Diem's.

This may have been partly due to the difference in the time of the summer in which the counts were made. But, the pelicans were successful in producing over 200 young that year. The numbers should have remained fairly constant with the adults remaining in the area to provide food for the young, or increased in the late summer with the addition of the young to the population. In 1974 the pelicans did not produce any young. This would account for the low numbers at the end of the summer since the adults probably moved out of the area earlier than usual. The circumstances surrounding the unsuccessful year may account for the differences in the June figures. High water and other factors produced conditions which were not ideal for nesting. Perhaps a smaller percentage of adults than usual actually nested and thus would not be picked up in Diem's count of breeders. In addition, immature pelicans use the lake during June, then migrate farther north (Diem pers. comm.). Again these would not appear in Diem's localized counts, but would be included in the wider one.

The gulls produced young in 1973; thus numbers should have remained fairly constant through the summer, or possibly increased in August with the recruitment of young into the population. Yet this author's estimate was only 75 percent of that obtained by Diem. This may be because it was virtually impossible to accurately count the hundreds of moving birds on the Molly Islands.

In both years late summer counts of terns were much lower than June counts. This may be due to the fact that in neither year did the

terns produce young. The adults, having no reason to remain on the lake, would decrease in numbers from June to August. Differences between the two population estimates obtained in June 1974 could have been due to a phenomenon similar to that conjectured for the pelicans. With adverse conditions it is possible that not all the terns nested. These non-breeders were picked up by the lake-wide count.

In 1974 the numbers of cormorants did not change from June to August. Apparently their numbers, unlike the pelicans or terns, remained constant even though they did not produce young either year. This would explain why independent counts in 1973, although made at different times of the summer, were similar.

A difference in the time of the censuses does not appear to be the main cause of differences between the author's and Swenson's eagle population estimates. This population is fairly constant through the summer, perhaps increasing toward the end as pairs from other parts of the park, unsuccessful in nesting, move to the lake. Thus, the lower estimate was probably due to visibility factors mentioned above.

Osprey populations also remain fairly constant through the summer, increasing slightly toward the end as the young fledge. In 1973 the author's population estimate was lower than Swenson's in part because Frank Island was not included in the sample of areas censused. This was not compensated for in the expansion of numbers as there was such a large percentage of ospreys in this area. In addition, the differences in the independent population estimates were probably due to

visibility factors.

The trends which occurred when all four census periods were compared were probably due to patterns in fall migration. The pelicans, terns, and cormorants were no longer in the counts because by October they had left the park (Diem and Condon 1967). Ospreys, mergansers, grebes, buffleheads, gulls, herons, and kingfishers decreased in numbers because they had begun migration out of the park (Bent 1919, 1923, Skinner 1925, Oberholser 1930, Munro 1942, Diem and Condon 1967, Swenson pers. comm.). An increase in goldeneye, eagle, and loon numbers may have been because they were still near the peak of their fall migration.

Distribution of these species will largely be determined by the location of their seasonal needs. The location of breeding birds will be dictated primarily by nesting sites and isolation from predators and disturbances, and secondarily by a food source. Distribution of non-breeders will be governed more by the fulfillment of their satisfactions and avoidance of their dissatisfactions.

Pelicans, cormorants, gulls, and terns all nest on Yellowstone Lake. They are colonial nesters and prefer rocky islands for nesting (Bent 1921, 1922, Hall 1925, Mendall 1936, Peterson 1961). Since human disturbance of these birds reportedly has detrimental effects on their breeding success (Murphy 1959), this may explain the large numbers of these birds on and near the Molly Islands in the remote portions of the

Southeast Arm. Even so, pelicans and gulls were found to forage away from the nesting area (Hall 1925, Rothwiler 1960, Schaller 1963).

Suitable nest sites on the lake seem to be the main factor influencing the distribution of kingfishers. Preferred nesting sites are those in steep sandy-clay banks (Peterson 1935, Bent 1940, White 1953, Cornwell 1963), and the only suitable bank seen is on the north shore. Most kingfishers were observed along the north shore. Observations of this bird on the west shore could be accounted for by the fact that they will fly up to five miles to a suitable fishing area (White 1953, Cornwell 1963).

The distribution of nesting ospreys is initially determined by the choice of nest sites. Nests are usually located at the tops of dead trees, on the lee side of an island or lakeshore (Peterson 1961, Swenson pers. comm.); isolation from humans also seems to play a part in the choice of nest sites (Swenson 1974). This explains why ospreys are frequently found in the arms and near Frank Island.

Most mergansers on Yellowstone Lake are non-breeders. They are also a species wary of human presence (Sayler and Langler 1940, pers. obs.). Thus their preferred location may be governed by remoteness and available food. Both of these are found in the arms and southern part of the lake.

The majority of goldeneyes and buffleheads are also non-breeders. Since they do not appear as wary of humans as the mergansers, their

distribution may be determined largely by food availability. They prefer fairly shallow water for feeding (Bent 1925, Erskine 1973), and thus would be found close to shore, in bays, at the mouths of inflowing streams, etc. These kinds of areas are most numerous inside the arms and along the southern shores of the main lake and the Thumb.

Fall staging behavior may explain the large numbers of grebes on the open waters of Yellowstone Lake in the late summer.

A general wariness of humans may account in part for the lesser number of waterbirds in the northern part of the lake since this is the part that receives the heaviest fisherman use. The east shore, although inaccessible to great numbers of people, is unsuitable because of wave action caused by the prevailing south-westerly winds. Instead the birds prefer the relative remote and protected arms, bays in the southern end of the lake, and lee side of Frank Island.

It was noted in the results section that mergansers probably eat between 0.44 and 0.66 lb fish/day, these fish averaging 8.5 in. However, fish of this size cannot account for the entire diet of the mergansers. Fish seen brought to the surface to be eaten were not numerous enough to satisfy the number of mergansers being watched. It is most likely that they are also taking fish small enough to be swallowed under the water, as has been reported by White (1937, 1957) and Sayler and Langler (1940). It is also possible, based on observations of them feeding in shallow water and among vegetation, that

they supplement their diet to some extent with invertebrates. This occurrence has been reported by others (Bent 1923, Munro and Clemens 1937, Kortright 1943).

While the diet of goldeneyes and buffleheads in Yellowstone National Park can only be conjectured about, it seems likely that they take mostly invertebrates. These birds were observed most often in water shallow enough for bottom feeding, and even when observed in deeper water in the South Arm, they were within reach of *Potamogeton* sp. Others have noted these birds feeding in such areas, and stated that they were feeding on invertebrates attached to the plants (Munro 1918, Bent 1925). Although the above is purely speculation, nothing has been observed to indicate that the diet of these species is significantly different from what other researchers have reported (Munro 1918, Bent 1925, Cottam 1939, Wiemeyer 1967, Erskine 1972).

Since the projected number of birds to be collected was so small, it was essential to take only birds with full stomachs. The first attempt indicated this was going to be a difficult task. The three mergansers were shot just before dusk in an area where they had previously been seen feeding and loafing. The assumption that such birds would have full stomachs was invalid. It became apparent that one would have to watch a group as they fed, and collect them shortly thereafter. But, given the limitations of time, finding feeding birds where they could be observed for a period of time at a range and location

within which they could be discreetly taken, it was decided that it was impractical to collect the remaining nine birds.

The sizes of fish as determined from the bones collected from the Molly Islands indicated a bias toward large fish. This was probably because it was easier to see and pick up larger bones. Since not every bone was collected, nothing can be concluded about the sizes of fish taken by the four species which use the Molly Islands. But, it would seem reasonable that the collection provided a representative sample of the species composition of the fish taken.

Noted in the results section was the total biomass of cutthroat trout consumed by piscivorous avifauna on Yellowstone Lake. A portion of this consists of fish less than 6 in. long. The maximum size taken by kingfishers is 5 in., by grebes 5 in., by goldeneyes 4 in., by loons 6 in., by terns 5 in., and it is unlikely that buffleheads take fish larger than 4-5 in. It is questionable whether predation on salmonids this size has any effect on the size of the adult population, because for the most part mortality is density-dependent during this period of their life history (Johnson 1965, LeCren 1965, Chapman 1966, Backiel and LeCren 1967, McFadden 1969, Mills 1969). Removal of this nature has little, if any, effect on recruitment of young into the adult segment.

In cutthroat trout mortality among the young must be considered during two different phases of their early life history, that mortality which occurs while the young are migrating from the spawning area to

the lake, and that which occurs in the lake.

There is a 98.4 percent mortality during the period between the emergence of the fry from the gravel and their entrance into Yellowstone Lake (Ball and Cope 1961). Mortality during this period is considered to be due mainly to predation and thus to be inversely density-dependent (Ricker 1952, Neave 1953, LeCren 1965, Johnson 1965, McFadden 1969). Benson (1960) found, however, that the strength of a given spawning year-class of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake showed no correlation with the strength of the corresponding immature year-class, the strength of the latter being measured as the fry migrated to the lake. A small or large number of immatures in a given year did not result in a respective small or large number of spawners returning to their home stream three years later. This suggests that the number of immatures reaching maturity is not determined by mortality occurring during lakeward migration.

A 36 percent mortality occurs among young cutthroats in Yellowstone Lake (Ball and Cope 1961), suggesting that mortality during migration was not of such a high degree to prevent a surplus recruitment into the next stage. While studies have not been done on the cutthroat, they have been on sockeye salmon which has an early life history similar to that of the cutthroat. These studies showed that during lake residence, mortality is density-dependent (Ricker 1941, Foerster 1944, Johnson 1961, 1965, Krogius 1962).

Thus two types of mortality occur among young cutthroat trout. The first, though not density-dependent, does not have an effect on the number of immatures reaching maturity. The second is density-dependent, also having no effect on the ultimate numbers of young recruited into the adult population.

It can be concluded, therefore, that those species of birds which prey on fish smaller than 5-6 in. (yearling size) do not have any effect on the size of the adult cutthroat population. While a portion of the diet of most of the species under consideration probably consists of this size fish, the entire diet of the goldeneyes, buffleheads, grebes, loons, terns, and kingfishers fall into this category. Thus, while the total consumption by piscivorous avifauna on Yellowstone Lake was 257,967 lb in 1973 and 184,635 lb in 1974, their net consumption was only 224,993 lb in 1973, and 144,233 lb in 1974.

APPENDIX

Figure 3. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of ospreys during three census periods.

Figure 4. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of mergansers during three census periods.

Figure 5. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of grebes during three census periods.

Figure 6. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of goldeneyes during three census periods.

Figure 8. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of eagles during three census periods.

Figure 9. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of gulls during three census periods.

Figure 10. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of loons during three census periods.

Figure 11. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of cormorants during three census periods.

Figure 12. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of herons during three census periods.

Figure 13. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of terns during three census periods.

Figure 14. Map of Yellowstone Lake showing the distribution of kingfishers during three census periods.

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